

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF INFLUENCING FACTORS IN ENSURING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF GRADUATES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The article explores the theoretical practical aspect of graduate competitiveness in higher education institutions. In the study, the concepts of competitiveness, higher education competitiveness and competitiveness of a graduate of a higher educational institution were systematized on the basis of the approaches of foreign and domestic scientists. At the same time, the main indicators of Higher Education Institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012-2021 were analyzed and the trends of change were evaluated. The factors affecting the level of competitiveness of graduates in the specialty they are studying at Fergana State University were evaluated through factors combined into 4 groups based on the main parameters determining the prestige of universities.

Keywords: competition, competitiveness of higher education institutions, competitiveness of graduates, market of educational services, influencing factors, higher education system, human capital

The changes in the socio-economic policy of the countries of the world are leading to serious changes in the system of higher education at the global level. The experience of countries such as Japan, Finland, South Korea, Germany, the United States, the PRC and the United Kingdom, where the higher education system has a high potential, indicates that these countries are growing steadily, influenced by the quality and competitiveness of specialists for whom the level of economic growth is being prepared.

In order for specialists trained in higher education institutions to meet the requirements of Personnel customers and today's socio-economic systems, the innovation of the higher education system requires the implementation of such changes as deepening the integration of activities into education, increasing the level of adaptability of educational programs to the changes taking place, increasing the qualification competencies of graduates.

A high level of attention is paid to the development of the higher education system in Uzbekistan in connection with modern changes, increasing the coverage and quality of Higher Education. In particular, in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 on the development of the National higher education system "...bringing the level of coverage with higher education to 50 percent and improving the quality of education, targeted training of potential higher education institutions to enter the international ratings of QS and TNE"¹ functions specified. The effective implementation of these tasks entails the development of a strategic management process for the training of competitive personnel in higher educational

¹ Development strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 60 PF of January 28, 2022 (Section IV, objectives 46-47) // www.lex.uz.

institutions, improvement of the strategy for the training of competitive personnel in higher educational institutions, assessment of the competitiveness of higher educational institutions, competitiveness of trained specialists, as well as improvement of mechanisms for its improvement, as well as scientific.

Highly qualified personnel are important in the sustainable development of the economy of our republic, and their training and retraining are directly related to the educational process. The educational process affects social, economic, cultural and other areas of activity. Education belongs to one of the most important manifestations of human activity, and the educational process is a process that has the property of continuity, starting with the birth of a person in practice throughout his life.

The higher education system of the field of educational services differs from other systems of the industry in that it prepares specialists in a narrow field for society, and the activities of these specialists in ensuring the effectiveness of activities of enterprises, organizations and institutions within the branches and sectors of the economy. Especially in today's period, with the move of economic development to an innovative basis, the demand for specialists being prepared by the higher education system is further expanded, requiring them to base the approach to situations on independent decisions, implement processes with low costs using innovations, increase labor productivity in processes. This requires the training of competitive personnel from functioning higher education institutions with good quality, high professional qualifications, able to practically adapt to processes.

The development of human capital not only increases the well-being of the population, but also increases the efficiency of the economy, labor productivity. The importance of attracting students to the national education system and giving them knowledge, being cultured by an individual, being a leading specialist in science, technology, production and other fields is invaluable. Economically, the integration of Science, Education and business is a necessary condition for development in the conditions of an innovative economy [1].

Uzbekistan is among the countries that can be globally competitive in the field of science, intellectual potential, modern personnel, High Technologies. Realizing that it is important to build our competitive future, the formation of professionals who meet the requirements of competitiveness should be the focus of our attention.

Literature analysis

In an in-depth study of the concept of competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions, it is advisable, first of all, to thoroughly study the concepts of "competition" and "competitiveness".

The word "competition" is considered a term of Arabic origin, and its dictionary translation means "control, observation". In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language to this term: "the struggle between independent producers of goods (enterprises) in the economic sense to produce goods in favorable conditions and sell them at a price of good profit, in general, in the economy, to strengthen its position"², described as.

The term "competition" comes from the Latin word "concurrentia" - collision, in the general sense that competition refers to the fact that individuals, groups, organizations

²Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language. A.Under Madvaliev Ed. - T.: State National publishing house" National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan".2008. 360 P.

compete among themselves to achieve relatively better results in a particular environment³.

N.In beknozov's research, competition consists of a clash of economic interests of market entities, interpreted as a struggle between them to have higher profits and more sophistication [2].

Competition is the competition of economic entities (competitors), in which their independent actions exclude or limit the possibility of each of them to unilaterally influence the general conditions of commodity circulation in the commodity or financial market in a single way⁴.

Economist scientists K.Kholikov and R.According to dusanov, competition is a process consisting in the struggle of participants in economic activity to maximally satisfy their needs and interests, get a good income, strengthen their position in the market, show their capabilities and have an image [3].

P.S.Zavyalov describes in his research the concept of competitiveness: "by competitiveness – it is necessary to understand the set of consumer and value descriptions that ensure the market popularity of a good, that is, the ability to exchange the same good for money under conditions when the offer to exchange similar competing goods is large"[4].

R.A.According to fathutdinov's opinion: "the competitiveness of Higher Education is its following ability:

1. Training specialists who will cope with the struggle of competition in a clear external and internal labor market;
2. Being able to create a novelty that can withstand competition in its field;
3. It consists in conducting a policy of effective reproduction in the activities of all its fields"[5].

Philip g of foreign scientists. In Altbach's research, it is argued that the overall ranking of universities in the higher education system is to some extent one of the main factors that determine the competitiveness of graduates of this university [6].

Summarizing the above approaches and opinions of various researchers, it is advisable to give the following generalized definition to the concept of competitiveness of a graduate of higher education institutions: "the competitiveness of a graduate of a higher educational institution is a set of professional, psychological and moral characteristics that determine the place of a graduate who graduated from an educational institution in the labor market"⁵.

Analysis and results

The development trends of world countries indicate that the level of development of different countries is changing in accordance with the level of development of the education system in these countries, in particular in the higher education system. Because in the period until the end of the 20th century, the development of the higher education system was carried out with a certain delay (the period until the graduation of specialists admitted to the higher education system), in the conditions of today's innovation development, this delay period is

³Иллюстрированный энциклопедический словарь (электронное издание, воспроизведенное по изданию 1995 года). — М., 1997. Худди шу мазмундаги изоҳ инглиз луғатларида ҳам келтирилади: Longman dictionary of contemporary English. - Edinburgh, 2001. - P. 270.

⁴ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on competition" // Tashkent, January 6, 2012, ORC,-No. 319.

⁵ Developed by the author.

minimized, that is, the process of training specialists is simultaneously realized with the creation[7].

Changes over the past 10 years indicate that more development is being achieved in our country's higher education system than changes over the previous 20 years (Table 1).

The above trend is also evident in the change in the number of higher education institutions operating in our republic. In 2012, the number of institutions of higher education was 64, while for 10 years the number increased 2.4 times to 154. The period of a sharp increase in the number of higher education institutions begins in 2018, and from this year to the present period, the growth of this cottage is more than 2 times.

The number of newly established foreign higher education institutions along with National Higher Education Institutions has also increased dramatically during the analyzed period. If in 2012 there were 6 Foreign higher education institutions or their branches in our country, then by the end of 2021 their number increased by 4.2 times to 25.

1- table

Changes in the main indicators of higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2012 - 2021⁶

(per school year)

Specification	Academic year										2021/2022 in the academic year compared to the 2012/2013 academic year, Times
	2012 / 2013	2013 / 2014	2014 / 2015	2015 / 2016	2016 / 2017	2017 / 2018	2018 / 2019	2019 / 2020	2020 / 2021	2021 / 2022	
Number of higher education institutions, unit	64	66	68	69	70	72	98	119	127	154	2,4
Including: number of foreign higher education institutions, unit	6	6	7	7	7	7	10	16	18	25	4,2
Number of students in	258,3	259,3	261,3	264,3	268,3	297,7	360,2	441,0	571,5	808,4	3,1

⁶ Developed by the author based on the data of the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

higher education institutions, thousand people												
Of which:	258,3	258,9	261,0	263,9	267,9	287,5	313,0	360,1	441,9	553,9	x	
in the form of full-time education	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,4	0,4	10,2	46,0	73,6	118,1	228,0	x	
in the form of correspondence education	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,2	7,3	11,5	26,5	x	
in the form of evening education	86	85	84	84	84	93	110	130	165	229	2,7	
The number of OTM students per 10,000 population, per capita	63,1	62,3	64,1	63,0	61,2	63,0	114,5	138,1	174,9	235,9	3,7	
The number of students admitted to higher education institutions, thousand people	60,9	60,5	67,6	66,3	64,1	67,4	70,3	70,8	83,9	103,9	1,7	

The number of students studying in full-time, evening and correspondence forms of Education also increased in proportion to the number of institutions of higher education in the time period in which the analysis was carried out. If in 2012 the number of students enrolled in existing higher education institutions was 258.3 thousand, then at the end of 2021 their number increased 3.1 times to 808.4 thousand.

Today, as a result of reforms in the higher education system of our country, all higher education institutions are trying, first, to increase their prestige in national and international rating systems, and secondly, to ensure the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market, which are among the most important factors in increasing their prestige. Currently, the level of competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions carrying out educational services and research activities in our country is estimated on the basis of the indicator of their initial post-education employment, as in the system of higher education of most developing countries. However, analyzes show that in most national higher education institutions, monitoring of changes after the initial employment of graduates is not carried out

at the required level, that is, the employment status of graduates after a certain period (half a year, one year) is not analyzed at the appropriate level (continuing activities in their specialty, Continuing Studies in second higher education or This brings a one-sided approach to assessing the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions and leads to a certain decrease in the prestige of higher education institutions in the next period[8,9].

Taking into account the above circumstances, in the process of carrying out the research, the factors affecting the formation of the competitiveness of specialists being prepared at Fergana State University were analyzed.

Taking into account the receipt of the initial employment rate of graduates as the main indicator of the competitiveness of specialists being trained in national higher education institutions operating in the educational services market, it is recommended to use an integral indicator expressed in the form of a geometric mean of indicators, expanding the factors obtained to assess this indicator based on a certain improvement in the

Today, it is advisable to assess the factors affecting the level of competitiveness of graduates in the specialty they are studying in higher education institutions through factors combined into the following 4 groups, based on the main parameters determining the prestige of universities:

1- group factor-the coefficient of initial employment of graduates of higher educational institutions. This factor indicator is currently present in the composition of the indicators that are collected for assessing the national rating of higher education institutions, and it is recommended to take this indicator in the form of a coefficient for an integral indicator. In general, mathematically, the initial employment coefficient of graduates of higher education institutions can be determined in the form of the following link:

$$K_{\text{ошж}} = \frac{B_{\text{ошж}}}{B_{\text{ym}}} \quad (1)$$

Here: $K_{\text{ошж}}$ – the initial employment coefficient of graduates of higher educational institutions is determined by the ratio of the number of graduates who are located at the initial employment to the total number of graduates;

B_{ym} – total number of graduates;

$B_{\text{ошж}}$ – the number of graduates who settled in the initial work.

To determine the level of the first group factor, indicators of the higher education institution selected for analysis, representing the employment level of graduates of 2018-2020, are used (Table 2).

2- table

Indicators on the number of graduates and their employment in 2018-2020 at Fergana State University⁷

Years	The total number of graduates, there are	The number of graduates who were placed in the initial job, the number of	Initial employment coefficient of its graduates

⁷ Developed by the author from the data of Fergana State University for 2018-2020.

2018	1566	1507	0,962
2019	1660	1552	0,935
2020	1540	1326	0,861

The coefficients of Fergana State University, which are considered the key factor parameter of the competitiveness integral indicator, calculated by 2018-2020, were determined.

$$K_{\text{ошж}}(2018_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \frac{B_{\text{ошж}}}{B_{\text{ум}}} = 0,962$$

$$K_{\text{ошж}}(2019_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \frac{B_{\text{ошж}}}{B_{\text{ум}}} = 0,935$$

$$K_{\text{ошж}}(2020_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \frac{B_{\text{ошж}}}{B_{\text{ум}}} = 0,861$$

Group 2 factors-a generalized coefficient of factors of the educational-methodological process affecting the competitiveness of graduates. Among the indicators of this group of factors, it is advisable to include the following factors that directly affect the level of educational quality through the educational process:

- qualification quality ratio of graduates in the final state attestation ($K_{\text{яда}}$). This coefficient is determined by the ratio of the number of graduates who showed "excellent" and "good" results in the final state attestation to the total number of graduates who participated;
- the coefficient of provision of the educational process with literature ($K_{\text{ат}}$). This coefficient is the average level of the provision of educational literature of all educational subjects according to the established norm (1 literature per 6 students);
- coefficient of proportion of students participating in academic exchange programs ($K_{\text{таа}}$). This coefficient is determined by the ratio of the number of students participating in academic exchange programs to the total number of students;
- number of published educational and methodological and scientific literature corresponding to one professor (A_c). This indicator is determined by the ratio of the number of educational and methodological and scientific literature published during the year to the number of professors.

Factors of the educational and methodological process established as parameters of the factor are considered factors that form the main qualitative signs of competition in graduates of higher educational institutions, which form the competencies of professional qualifications in their specialty in graduates within the framework of the established standards.

The generalized coefficient of the factors of the educational-methodological process (to determine the geometric mean of the indicators of the factor belonging to the group to be obtained minimizes the deviations in the variation of the indicators, and it can be expressed in the form of the following link:

$$K_{\text{yy}} = \sqrt[4]{K_{\text{яда}} \cdot K_{\text{ат}} \cdot K_{\text{таа}} \cdot A_c} \quad (2)$$

To determine the degree of factors of the second group, indicators of Fergana State University, representing the result of the educational and methodological process of 2018-2020, are used (Table 3).

3- table

Factor indicators representing educational and methodological processes affecting the competitiveness of graduates in 2018-2020 at Fergana State University⁸

Years	Qualification quality ratio of graduates in the final state attestation	The coefficient of provision of the educational process with literature	Coefficient of proportion of students participating in academic exchange programs	Number of published educational and methodological and scientific literature corresponding to one professor
2018	0,79	0,91	0,002	0,09
2019	0,73	0,94	0,001	0,08
2020	0,82	0,96	0,006	0,11

We determine the coefficients of the factors of the generalized educational and methodological process affecting the competitiveness of graduates for 2018-2020 at Fergana State University:

$$K_{\ddot{y}y}(2018_{\Phi\text{ap}\Delta y}) = \sqrt[4]{0,79 \cdot 0,91 \cdot 0,002 \cdot 0,09} = 0,107$$

$$K_{\ddot{y}y}(2019_{\Phi\text{ap}\Delta y}) = \sqrt[4]{0,73 \cdot 0,91 \cdot 0,001 \cdot 0,08} = 0,085$$

$$K_{\ddot{y}y}(2020_{\Phi\text{ap}\Delta y}) = \sqrt[4]{0,82 \cdot 0,96 \cdot 0,006 \cdot 0,11} = 0,151$$

Group 3 factors-a generalized coefficient of scientific and innovative factors affecting the competitiveness of graduates ($K_{\text{ин}}$). These group factors directly and indirectly affect the formation of R & D skills for the elimination of specific situational or systemic problems in the trained specialists, at the same time for the sustainable development of basic activities in the field direction, and among the factors of this group it is advisable to include the following factors:

- coefficient of scientific potential of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions ($K_{\text{ис}}$). This coefficient is determined by the ratio of the number of professors with a scientific degree (title) operating in a higher educational institution to the total number of professors;

- coefficient of professors and teachers who have received a scientific degree and a scientific title ($K_{\text{идп}}$, annual result is obtained). This indicator is determined by the ratio of the number of professors who have received a scientific degree (title) during the year to the total number of professors;

- number of scientific articles per professor ($Q_{\text{им}}$). This indicator is determined by the ratio of the number of articles published by professors in international and Republican scientific journals throughout the year to the total number of professors;

- funds received from scientific research per professor ($Q_{\text{итм}}$, 10 mln. Soum). This indicator is determined by the ratio of the amount dropped from International, Republican and local sources of financing of research activities during the year to the total number of professors.

Factors included in the third group, while expressing the degree to which teachers teaching students can directly apply the skills of teaching research methods in the educational

⁸ Developed by the author from the data of Fergana State University for 2018-2020.

process, organizing and carrying out research and being able to introduce research results, also have an impact on the formation of qualifications required in this direction to the trained specialists. In other words, the necessary qualifications and skills for developing scientifically based conclusions and making decisions by students in specific situations can be explained under the influence of factors included in the third group, and these qualifications and skills provide a competitive advantage in the scientific and innovative direction in graduates.

It is recommended to calculate the generalized coefficient of scientific and innovative factors affecting the competitiveness of graduates using the following link under the Fergana State University, selected for analysis for 2018-2020:

$$K_{ии} = \sqrt[4]{K_{ис} \cdot K_{идп} \cdot Q_{им} \cdot Q_{итм}} \quad (3)$$

To determine the generalized coefficient of factors of the third group, indicators of higher education institutions selected for analysis, representing the scientific and innovative activities of 2018-2020, are used (Table 4).

4- Table

Factor indicators representing scientific and innovative activities affecting the competitiveness of graduates in 2018-2020 at Fergana State University⁹

Years	Coefficient of scientific potential of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions	Coefficient of professors and teachers who have received a scientific degree and a scientific title	Number of scientific articles per professor	Funds received from scientific research per professor (10 million. Soum)
2018	0,291	0,038	0,225	0,235
2019	0,264	0,043	0,554	0,254
2020	0,235	0,030	0,932	0,197

For 2018-2020 at Fergana State University, we determine the coefficients of generalized scientific and innovative activity factors affecting the competitiveness of graduates:

$$K_{ии}(2018_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,291 \cdot 0,038 \cdot 0,225 \cdot 0,235} = 0,156$$

$$K_{ии}(2019_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,264 \cdot 0,043 \cdot 0,554 \cdot 0,254} = 0,2$$

$$K_{ии}(2020_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,235 \cdot 0,030 \cdot 0,932 \cdot 0,197} = 0,19$$

Group 4 factors-a generalized coefficient of international relations affecting the competitiveness of graduates ($K_{ха}$). These group factors also have a direct and indirect effect on the professional qualifications and personal and psychological characteristics of graduates trained in higher education institutions, and among the factors of this group it is advisable to include the following two factors:

- ratio of the share of foreign teachers ($K_{х\bar{y}}$). This indicator is determined by the ratio of the number of professors involved in the educational process from abroad to the total number of professors;

⁹ Developed by the author from the data of Fergana State University for 2018-2020.

- proportion coefficient of foreign students (K_{XT}). This coefficient is determined by the ratio of the number of foreign students studying at a higher educational institution to the total number of students during the analysis period.

It is recommended to calculate the generalized coefficient of international indicators affecting the competitiveness of graduates using the following link on Bukhara State University and Fergana State University, selected for analysis by 2018-2020:

$$K_{\text{ин}} = \sqrt{K_{\text{xy}} \cdot K_{\text{xt}}} \quad (4)$$

To determine the generalized coefficient of factors of the fourth group, indicators representing international relations of higher education institutions of 2018-2020, selected for analysis, are used (Table 5).

5- Table

Indicators of the factor representing international relations affecting the competitiveness of graduates in 2018-2020 at Fergana State University¹⁰

Years	Ratio of the share of foreign teachers	Proportion coefficient of foreign students
2018	0,003	0,002
2019	0,007	0,001
2020	0,005	0,002

We will determine the coefficients of generalized international relations affecting the competitiveness of graduates for 2018-2020 in Fergana State University:

$$K_{\text{ин}}(2018_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt{0,003 \cdot 0,002} = 0,0024$$

$$K_{\text{ин}}(2019_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt{0,007 \cdot 0,001} = 0,0026$$

$$K_{\text{ин}}(2020_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt{0,005 \cdot 0,002} = 0,001$$

We determine the integral coefficient of competitiveness of graduates by higher education institutions using the generalized coefficients determined for 2018-2020 by grouped factors.

When determining the integral coefficient of competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions, we use the geometric mean of the group generalized coefficients. The integral coefficient of the competitiveness of graduates is determined based on the following link:

$$K_{\text{инт}} = \sqrt[n]{\sum_1^n K_i} \quad (5)$$

Here: K_i – generalized coefficients by Factor groups;

n – number of groups.

In order to facilitate the process of calculating the integral coefficient of graduate competitiveness, we take into a separate table the generalized coefficients calculated according to the groups of the above 4 factors, as well as determine the integral coefficients of graduate competitiveness by the years being analyzed using the (5)-link (Table 6).

6- Table

Generalized group coefficients and integral coefficient indicators affecting the competitiveness of graduates in 2018-2020 according to Fergana State University¹¹

Years	Initial	Generalized	Generalized	Generalized	Alumni
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¹⁰ Developed by the author from the data of Fergana State University for 2018-2020.

¹¹ Developed by the author in the research process.

	employment coefficient of graduates	coefficient of educational-methodological process factors	coefficient of scientific and innovative factors	coefficient of international relations	competitiveness integral coefficient
2018	0,962	0,107	0,156	0,0024	0,079
2019	0,935	0,085	0,200	0,0026	0,080
2020	0,861	0,151	0,190	0,0010	0,071

The integral coefficient of competitiveness of graduates at Fergana State University was as follows by year:

$$K_{\text{инт}}(2018_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,962 \cdot 0,107 \cdot 0,156 \cdot 0,0024} = 0,079$$

$$K_{\text{инт}}(2019_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,935 \cdot 0,085 \cdot 0,200 \cdot 0,0026} = 0,080$$

$$K_{\text{инт}}(2020_{\text{ФарДУ}}) = \sqrt[4]{0,861 \cdot 0,151 \cdot 0,190 \cdot 0,001} = 0,071$$

Based on the above calculations and analyzes, an attempt was made to improve the assessment methodology, taking into account the influence of factors on the competitiveness of graduates of higher education institutions operating in the educational services market of our country today, that is, to expand the range of indicators of the factor used in the methodology. While this methodology, which allows us to thoroughly assess the competitiveness of graduates of National Higher Education Institutions on an existing basis taking into account the influence of factors, in essence does not allow a Real and full-fledged assessment of the competitiveness of graduates, we believe that this improved methodology can be used in practice. To further improve the proposed methodology, it is required to include in National Higher Education Institutions a number of indicators that are taken into account today in the assessment methodology used in higher education institutions with high prestige in developed countries (the degree of dual degree of graduates, the number of students with prizes at the international level, Nobel laureates, the number of multi-profile graduates).

References:

1. Володин Н. Аграрный туризм — это полноценный отдых на родной земле II Сайт Калужской областной газеты «Знамя» [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://znamkaluga.ru/content/view/2262/2/> (дата обращения 12.10.2012).
2. Барлыбаев А. Агротуризм в Башкортостане / А. Барлыбаев, Г. Насыров // Экономика сельского хозяйства. -93.
3. Биржаков М. Б. Организация сельского туризма: практическое пособие / М. Б. Биржаков, Л. И. Биткулова, Д. Н. Панова. Всеволожск: ЕЛГО, 2010.
4. Чайка В. Сельский туризм в устойчивом развитии сельских территорий В. Чайка, А. Исаев // Экономика сельского хозяйства России. 2010. №11. С. 23-25.
5. Мирзаев А.Т. Ўзбекистонда туристик-рекреация фаолиятини бошқариш методологиясини такомиллаштириш. Иқтисодий фанлари доктори (DSc.) илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. -Т.: ТДИУ, 2021. - 25 б.
6. Мирзаев А.Т. Туристтик-рекреация корхоналари фаолиятини бошқаришнинг иқтисодий самарадорлиги таҳлили // Иқтисодий ва таълим. -2019, №6. 214-219-б.

7.Mirzaev

A.T.

Assessment of cluster formation in management of recreational activity. International Scientific Journal "Theoretical & Applied Science", Philadelphia, USA. 04, (84), 2020. – 605-610-pp. -ISSN: 2308-4944. <http://T-Science.org>

8.Mirzaev A.T. Evaluation of innovation capacity resource components in effective management of recreational clusters on the basis of econometric analysis. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD). India. Volume: 5 Issue: 7 July 2020. –P.131-137. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra4790>

9.Мирзаев А.Т. Совершенствование системы электронного бронирования как часть цифровизации управленческой деятельности туристско-рекреационных предприятий. Бюллетень науки и практики. Нижневартовск, Россия. Т. 6. №8. 2020. – 99-104 б. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/57>

10.Мирзаев А.Т. Ўзбекистонда туристик-рекреация корхоналари фаолиятини бошқаришнинг ташкилий-иқтисодий механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Ишлаб чиқаришни кластер усулида ташкил этишнинг зарурияти. Бизнес-Daily медиа. -2020, №1. -62-65-б.

11.Мирзаев А.Т. Ўзбекистонда туристик-рекреация хизматларини бошқариш жараёнига омиллар таъсирини баҳолаш. Хитойда саноатлашувни жадаллаштиришда кластерлаш модели хусусиятлари. Бизнес-Daily медиа. -2020, №6. -57-61-б.

12.Мирзаев А.Т. Туристтик-рекреация кластерларини бошқаришда инновацион салоҳиятнинг ресурс компонентини баҳолаш услубиёти // Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар. -2020, №4. 4/2020 (№ 00048). 390-401 б. <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>

13.Мирзаев А.Т. Туристтик-рекреация хизматлар бозорида бошқарув тизимини ривожлантириш истиқболлари// Иқтисодиёт ва таълим. -2020, №4. 247-252-б.

14.Мирзаев А.Т. Рекреацион – туризм кластерларини яратиш ёхуд улар орқали ҳудудларда сайёҳлик тизимини ривожлантириш истиқболлари // Бизнес-эксперт. Фонд бозорлари фаолияти самараси ва унга тижорат банклари фаолияти таъсири. Бизнес-Daily медиа. -2017, №12. -21-24-б.

15.Мирзаев А.Т. Туристтик-рекреация объектлари кластерларини шакллантириш механизмларини баҳолаш // Иқтисодиёт ва таълим. -2018, №6. -207-213-б.

16.Мирзаев А.Т. Туристтик хизматлар бозорида рекреацион туризм хизматларига талабнинг ўзгаришлар таҳлили // Иқтисодиёт ва таълим. -2019, №1. 214-219-б.

17.Мирзаев А.Т. Оценка использования рекреационных возможностей на рынке туристических услуг // Региональная экономика: теория и практика - 2019. №5 (464). Россия. С.990-1002.

18.Мирзаев А.Т. Совершенствование интегральной оценки механизма рекреационно-туристических объектов // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2019. Т. 5. №2. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/39>. Нижневартовск, Россия. С.127-134.

19.Mirzaev, A.T. (2018) "The level of use of tourist attractions in the regions and the factors affecting them," Economics and Innovative Technologies: Vol. 2018: No.3, Article19. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/iqtisodiyot/vol2018/iss3/19>

20.Mirzaev A. T. Estimation of the prospects for the use of recreational facilities in the market of tourism services //Наука сегодня: вызовы, перспективы и возможности [Текст]. – 2018. – С. 76.

21. Mirzaev A.T. Туристик-рекреация кластерларини бошқаришда инновацион салоҳиятнинг ресурс компонентини баҳолаш услубиёти “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar” ilmiy elektron jurnali. № 4, iyul-avgust, 2020 yil. 390-401 б.
22. Мирзаев А.Т. Методологические основы развития и повышения конкурентоспособности туристско-рекреационной деятельности // Бюллетень науки и практики. 2021. Т. 7. №10. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/71/33>. Нижневартовск, Россия. С.283-293.
23. Mirzaev Abdullajon Topilovich. (2021). Economic evaluation of multiplicative efficiency on the basis of generalized indicators of resource components in tourist recreation activities. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(6), 107-114. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrds/article/view/1004>
24. Мирзаев А.Т. Туризм-рекреацияси хизматлар бозорида рақамлаштиришнинг ялпи талаб ўзгаришига таъсири таҳлили // Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар. - 2021, №3. 3/2021 (№ 00053). 386-397 б. <http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz>.
25. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Управление туристско-рекреационной деятельностью как фактор формирования стратегического планирования предпринимательства. In *Наука сегодня: теория и практика: Материалы международной научно-практической конференции*. Вологда (р. 21).
26. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Эффективные методы управления и государственной поддержки туристско-рекреационной сферы в узбекистане. *Наука сегодня: опыт, традиции, инновации [Текст]: материалы*, 41.
27. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Современные аспекты управления туристско-рекреационной сферой Республики Узбекистан. *Инновационные исследования как локомотив развития современной науки от теоретических парадигм к практике*, 312-318.
28. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2018). Рекреацион туризм хизматлари бозорини ривожлантириш орқали аҳоли бандлигини таъминлаш хусусиятлари. *Бизнес-Daily медиа*, (11), 63-66.
29. Mirzaev, A. (2019). Perfection of the integral evaluation of the mechanism of recreational and tourist objects. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*.
30. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2019). Ўзбекистон ҳудудларида туристик-рекреация объектларидан самарали фойдаланиш механизмини такомиллаштириш. Иқтисодиёт фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) диссертацияси автореферати. СамИСИ, 58.
31. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Туристик-рекреация фаолиятини бошқаришда электрон резервлар тизимидан фойдаланиш афзалликлари. *Xorazm ma'mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi*, (9), 99-104.
32. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2021). Теоретические аспекты развития процессов управления туристско-рекреационной деятельностью. *Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования*, 19.
33. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2018). Миллий ўйинлар орқали туристик кластерларни ривожлантириш. *Бизнес-Daily медиа*, (4), 83-85.
34. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). Инвестиционная составляющая развития туристического и рекреационного потенциала республики Узбекистан. *Наука сегодня: проблемы и перспективы развития [Текст]: ма*, 51.

35. Mirzaev, A. (2020). Improving the Electronic Booking System as a Part of Digitization of Management Activities of Recreational Enterprises. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 6(8), 165-172.
36. Topilovich, M. A. (2022). IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(10), 124-136.
37. Topilovich, M. A. (2022). HEALTHCARE FIELD MANAGEMENT AND ACTIVITY MULTIFACTOR MODEL BASED DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(08), 117-129.
38. Topilovich, M. A. MANAGEMENT OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN: ANALYSIS, TRENDS AND PROSPECTS.
39. Mirzaev, A. (2021). Туризм-рекреациясиси хизматлар бозорида рақамлаштиришнинг ялпи талаб ўзгаришига таъсири таҳлили. *Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar*, (3), 392-403.
40. Мирзаев, А. (2021). ХУДУДИЙ ТУРИСТИК-РЕКРЕАЦИЯ ФАОЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА БОШҚАРУВ ҚАРОРЛАРИ ҚАБУЛ ҚИЛИШ МЕТОДОЛОГИЯСИНИ КОГНИТИВ ЁНДАШУВ АСОСИДА ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. *Экономика и образование*, (5), 390-398.
41. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2021). Особенности развития рекреационной деятельности на рынке туристических услуг. *Наука сегодня: проблемы и перспективы развития* [Текст]: ма, 28.
42. Мирзаев, А. Т. (2020). ТУРИСТИК-РЕКРЕАЦИЯ КЛАСТЕРЛАРИДА ИННОВАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ КРОСС-ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР АСОСИДАГИ МОДЕЛИ. *Вестник КГУ им. Бердаха*. №, 4, 37.
43. Mirzaev, A. (2018). Худудларда туристик рекреация объектларидан фойдаланиш даражаси ва уларга таъсир этувчи омиллар таҳлили. *Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar*, (3), 164-170.
44. Topilovich, M. A. MANAGEMENT OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN: ANALYSIS, TRENDS AND PROSPECTS.
45. Хомидов, К. (2023). О'zbekistonda turistik majmualar faoliyatini boshqaruv samaradorligi oshirish yo'llari. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 11(3), 154-160.
46. Хомидов, Q. (2019). Кластер-действенный инструмент конкурентоспособности региона. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
47. Хомидов, Q. (2020). Iqtisodiyotni investitsiyaviy jozibadorligini oshirishda erkin iqtisodiy zonalarni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
48. Хомидов, Q. (2019). Iqtisodiyotimizni raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda innovatsion tadbirkorlikning o'rni va ahamiyati. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
49. Хомидов, Q. (2019). Aholi bandligi ta'minlash-iqtisodiy munosabatlarning muhim omili. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
50. Akhmedova, N. K., & ugli Homidov, K. K. (2022). Institutional Basis of Digitalization of Management Activity of Food Industry Enterprises in Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(11), 34-38.

- 51.Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Socioeconomic characteristics of employment in Uzbekistan. *Инновационная наука*, (7-8), 64-66.
- 52.Хомидов, К. К. (2019). Перспективный комплекс экономики Узбекистана. In *Современная мировая экономика: проблемы и перспективы в эпоху развития цифровых технологий и биотехнологии* (pp. 54-56).
- 53.Homidov, K. (2023). Conceptual approaches to the formation of a model for the sustainable development of tourist complexes. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(7), 33-38.
- 54.Homidov, K. (2023). Organizational and economic foundations of the organization of tourist complexes in the development of tourism in the regions. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(7), 44-50.
- 55.Homidov Kakhkhorali Kurbonali ugli. (2023). Objective need for the formation and sustainable development of tourist complexes in the regions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8151902>. *IQRO* , 4(2), 42-45.

